

Impact of Vocational Training on Economic Empowerment of Rural Women in Hyderabad

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Abstract: *This study investigates the effects of vocational training on the economic empowerment of rural women in Hyderabad, focusing on how skill development influences their decision-making capacity, financial independence, and overall quality of life. The main objectives of this study are to assess the effectiveness of vocational training in enhancing rural women's employability, also to evaluate the impact of vocational skills on women's ability to start and sustain small businesses. This study adopts qualitative approach, the data relies on Semi-structured interviews of 5 women to explore women's experiences, challenges, and perspectives on how vocational training has influenced their lives who have completed vocational trainings, rural women face unique barriers to economic empowerment, including limited access to formal education and employment opportunities, compounded by cultural stigmatization. This research examines various vocational training programs, such as tailoring, sewing, stitching, knitting, applique work, handicrafts, beauty and computer literacy and their effectiveness in enhancing women's income, employability, and entrepreneurial abilities. Key factors affecting program success—such as cultural barriers, access to training, and the availability of post-training support—are critically analyzed. Furthermore, the study highlights the broader community-level impact, showing how vocational training facilitates women's increased participation in the local economy. The research reveals that vocational training significantly improves rural women's employability, leading to higher income levels and more stable employment. Additionally, women who completed training programs reported an increased capacity to start small businesses and generate independent income. The findings also indicate that vocational training enhances women's confidence, decision-making abilities, and participation in household financial matters. Vocational training plays a crucial role in the economic empowerment of rural women by providing them with practical skills that improve their employability and entrepreneurial capabilities. The programs not only enhance women's financial independence but also elevate their self-esteem and decision-making power within their families. However, to maximize the impact of vocational training, greater focus should be placed on overcoming cultural barriers, ensuring accessibility, and providing post-training support.*

Keywords: *Economic Empowerment, Vocational Trainings, Rural Women, Women Entrepreneurship*

BACKGROUND

The empowerment of women in rural areas has long been recognized as a key factor in fostering economic and social development. In many rural communities, particularly in Pakistan, women face limited access to formal education, employment opportunities, and financial independence. Vocational training has been promoted as a solution to this issue, offering women practical skills that can improve their employability and entrepreneurship prospects. Vocational training is an important mechanism to integrate rural youth in society and to make them a dynamic member of the society Khalid, A. ., Aashiq, U. ., Iqbal, M. S. ., & Hassan, S. S. . (2020).

In the modern world skilled labor is need of the industrial sector. Vocational training enables the pass-outs to apply their skills practically in various trades. It focuses on enhancement of skills and expertise in student. It enhances students' skills in different trades and leads towards industrial, technological and economic development of a country. Vocational training and technical education institutions produce skilled labor to fulfill the demand of industry (Mathewes &Arulsamy, 2019). The empowerment of women is a key factor in achieving sustainable development, particularly in rural areas where socio-economic challenges are more prevalent. In India, rural women often face limited access to education, healthcare, and employment opportunities, which restricts their ability to contribute fully to their household income and local economy. Vocational training has emerged as a powerful tool to address these issues by providing women with the skills needed for employment and entrepreneurship. In Hyderabad, numerous organizations and government initiatives offer vocational training programs tailored for rural women. These programs range from tailoring and handicrafts to agricultural and technical skills. However, there is a need to assess the actual impact of such training on economic empowerment and whether it leads to sustainable employment or business opportunities. The study of Khanum et al. (2020) postulated that women's economic empowerment is critical for sustainable development because, without their involvement in mainstream development programs, it would be impossible to institutionalize the sustainable development process in Bangladesh. Women's empowerment is a major issue in global development; despite their great contribution to development, women face discrimination, especially in developing countries. Women are also treated worse than men owing to society's rules, norms, customs, and character. Andriamahery, A., & Qamruzzaman, M. (2022).

The study was undertaken with the following objectives:

1. To evaluate the impact of vocational training on the economic empowerment of rural women in Hyderabad.
2. To analyze the relationship between access to financial resources and the economic empowerment of rural women.
3. To investigate how social and cultural norms influence the participation of rural women in vocational training and their subsequent economic empowerment.
4. To explore the mediating role of self-esteem and confidence in the relationship between vocational training, access to financial resources, and economic empowerment among rural women.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What is the impact of vocational training on the economic empowerment of rural women in Hyderabad?
2. What is the relationship between access to financial resources and the economic empowerment of rural women?
3. How social and cultural norms influence the participation of rural women in vocational training

and their subsequent economic empowerment?

4. What is the mediating role of self-esteem and confidence in the relationship between vocational training, access to financial resources, and economic empowerment among rural women?

RESEARCH GAP

In the following study *The Impact of Vocational Training on the Economic Empowerment of Rural Hyderabad* is essential to understanding what areas remain unexplored or insufficiently studied. These gaps provide opportunities for further research and can help improve policies and programs targeting the economic empowerment of rural women. Below are potential research gaps in this area, while there may be studies on vocational training and economic empowerment in general, specific research focusing on rural Hyderabad is relatively scarce. Hyderabad has unique socio-cultural, economic, and demographic characteristics that influence the effectiveness of vocational training programs. A gap exists in understanding how these regional factors, including local industries, cultural norms, and community structures, affect the outcomes of vocational training programs for rural women.

SIGNIFICANCE

The significance of a study on the *Impact of Vocational Training on the Economic Empowerment of Rural Women in Hyderabad* lies in its potential to offer insights into how skill development can transform the lives of marginalized women in rural areas. This type of research has both practical and social relevance, particularly in regions like rural Hyderabad, where socio-economic challenges often limit women's opportunities for economic advancement. The study can demonstrate how vocational training equips rural women with the skills and knowledge needed to: Gain employment or start their own businesses. Increase their income, contributing to household financial stability. Achieve financial independence, reducing reliance on family members or spouses for economic support.

LITERATURE REVIEW

VOCATIONAL TRAINING

The economic contribution and empowerment of women are pertinent to strengthening female rights to enable them to have control over their lives and influence society too. Sustainable development can be achieved through the economic empowerment of women. Empowered women and gender equality lead to multiplying development efforts. Hence focusing on providing opportunities for learning and training be it formal or informal will increase their ability to contribute effectively to society. Tiwari, P., & Malati, N. (2023). Additionally Samoliuk, N., Bilan, Y., & Mishchuk, H. (2021) stated With the spread of vocational training practices at enterprises, their positive impact on economic benefits is quite theoretically and empirically proven not only for individuals and firms, but also for the country as a whole.

ACCESS TO FINANCIAL RESOURCES

A study conducted by Egbo et al. (2020) investigates the association between financial literacy and access to credit by women entrepreneurs in Nigeria. The study documented that financial knowledge was a key element in expanding women-owned businesses, particularly during start-up. Additionally, the study established that financial expertise is essential to the development and success of women-owned businesses.

While turning into influential entrepreneurs, women face different social difficulties from their relatives and society. Every business needs finance to start a business. Women have issues accessing advances from banks, money related organizations. They have too restricted in various SME divisions other than traditional organizations. Besides, because of the absence of technological skills, they cannot deal with

their records appropriately. Andriamahery, A., & Qamruzzaman, M. (2022).

SOCIAL AND CULTURAL NORMS

According to Bullough, A., Guelich, U., Manolova, T. S., & Schjoedt, L. (2022), The factors that influence women's entrepreneurship vary depending on circumstance and the dynamic nature of their complex and interconnected lives—in other words, cultural influences.

Thus, gender and culture dynamically interact, shaping gender role expectations and identities, and the economic and social environment in which women's entrepreneurship is embedded. Bullough, A., Guelich, U., Manolova, T. S., & Schjoedt, L. (2022).

Cultural norms play a crucial role in shaping the behavior and decision-making of entrepreneurs stated by (Farrukh et al., 2019).

SELF-ESTEEM AND CONFIDENCE

It is stated by Khan, R. U., Salamzadeh, Y., Shah, S. Z. A., & Hussain, M. (2021) Women entrepreneurs, who have a high self-confidence level, could quickly gain a competitive advantage in emerging markets while facing different barriers that need to set an objective on or plan a better policy to reach business goals.

According to Malureanu, A., Panisoara, G., & Lazar, I. (2021), Self-confidence implies a person's professed capability to tackle situations effectively on his own without leaning on others and to have constructive self-evaluation; self-confidence is an optimistic look at one's own self

ECONOMIC EMPOWERMENT

Empowering women means gaining the power to think and act freely, developing a sense of self-worth, believing in the ability to make the desired changes in oneself, the right to control one's life, the right to choose, the actualization of all women's potential and equality in society. Phala and Mukonza, (2021). Furthermore, Ataei et al., 2019; Mirzaei et al. (2011) Stated Empowerment is a component of sustainable development; empowerment is considered a factor in sustainable development; and empowerment is the result of sustainable development.

Women's empowerment and their work force participation are their fundamental rights, which enable them to have control over their lives and, in turn, mark their influence in society. Women can be truly empowered if they are provided with safety, education, healthcare, trust, vocational skills training, speaking out against violence and gender inequality, postpartum assistance for resuming work, upskilling or reskilling, societal mindset changes, and moral education for gender equality to boys in school. Vocational SD is indispensable for women's empowerment. Women's full participation in the workforce is essential to achieving gender equality and self-sustainability. Core responsibility lies with the elders of the family to break stereotypes and encourage men into care professions and women into the science, technology, engineering, mathematics, and skill sectors. Parveen, R. (2023).

According to Ebrahimi, R., Choobchian, S., Farhadian, H., Goli, I., Farmandeh, E., & Azadi, H. (2022). The scope of empowerment is such that all members of society, from the lowest level of development to the highest level of self-knowledge, are exposed. Rural women, as an effective factor in various agricultural activities have a significant share in the participation of the required manpower in the rural community, so that without their participation, it is impossible to achieve rural development. Rural organizations, as supportive and motivating factors, can also play an important role in empowering women, so that with the solutions and credits that these organizations provide, can take steps to build trust. Empowerment is a developmental issue, since women who are empowered will be able to act in broader aspects and play a more active role in all aspects to change in different ways, we must empower each idea to make a reasonable change to increase welfare for rural women. Empowering women needs to provide social contexts before the individual ones.

Previous research suggests that vocational training is a critical driver of economic empowerment for rural women. Studies by Sharma (2018) and Bhardwaj (2020) emphasize that vocational education provides women with market-relevant skills, which increases their chances of securing employment or initiating micro-enterprises. Vocational training programs are seen as instrumental in helping women break free from traditional domestic roles and participate in economic activities.

Additionally, literature on women’s entrepreneurship in rural India shows that vocational training not only enables women to gain financial independence but also boosts their confidence and decision-making power in the household. However, the long-term sustainability of small businesses run by women remains a challenge, as many women face difficulties in accessing markets, capital, and ongoing business support (Kumar, 2019).

METHODOLOGY

A qualitative research approach was adopted in this study. Thus; this method was suitable for the research conducted. Furthermore, qualitative research provides a rich, contextual, and detailed understanding of phenomena (Rahman, 2016). This is the type of investigation required by this topic, given that the factors that may influence a choice of career path are complex and are impacted by a myriad of factors. In addition, the rationale behind each individual’s choice is personal and unique to gain in-depth insights into the experiences of rural women who had undergone vocational training in Hyderabad. The sample comprised 5 rural women aged 18 to 50 from different areas of the Hyderabad district. The participants had completed vocational training programs in fields such as tailoring, handicrafts, agriculture, and small-scale business management. Purposive sampling was used to ensure a diverse representation of different skills, including tailoring, handicrafts, agricultural practices, and information technology. Additionally, they have five or more years’ experience. Purposive sampling has its own advantages of getting data from the sample you are sure of to provide the best experiences since you know its characteristics. The beauty with this sampling type is that the participants are handpicked by the researcher due to the relevant knowledge and experience the researcher has on the sample and topic. Nyimbili, F., & Nyimbili, L. (2024).

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

INTERVIEWS

This study used individual interviews and focus group interviews in gathering relevant data. These interviews were comprised of 7 questions along with brief introduction conducted over one week, and all interviews were recorded. The interviews with women were face to face and online carried out from 1 to 7 October, 2024 via telephone. All the interviews were conducted using a semi-structured approach (Kumar, 2011), allowing us to guide the discussion so that pertinent areas were addressed while enabling participants to express their thoughts freely. An interview is a verbal exchange in person, via telephone, or another medium to obtain an individual's perspective about a selected topic (Burns, 1997). Some advantages of interviews include information can be supplemented by nonverbal responses gleaned through observation, explanations can clarify misunderstandings, follow-up questions can be asked, and this method can be used with any population (Kumar, 2011). There were 5 individual interviews, each lasting approximately 15 minutes' responses were collected in Urdu language.

FINDINGS

One of the most prominent findings is that vocational training substantially improves the employability of rural women in Hyderabad. Women who acquired skills in tailoring, embroidery, and handicrafts were able to find employment with local businesses, while others used their skills to provide freelance services from home. For instance, women who completed training in tailoring mentioned that they now receive regular orders from local customers, allowing them to earn a stable income while managing household responsibilities.

Response 1

Since I completed the training, I've been able to earn some extra money by selling handmade products. It's not a huge income, but it helps pay for school supplies and groceries, and I feel proud to contribute.

While many women successfully started businesses, sustaining these ventures presented significant challenges. Participants highlighted the difficulty in accessing markets, especially in remote rural areas. Without reliable transportation or connections to larger markets, some women found it difficult to scale their businesses beyond local sales. Additionally, participants reported limited access to credit and financing, which hindered their ability to invest in equipment or raw materials for their businesses.

Response 2

The biggest challenge was to access the financial resources another issue was to find time to attend the sessions, as I have to manage household chores and take care of my children. Sometimes, I couldn't attend because of family responsibilities.

Response 3

The training center was a bit far from my village, making it hard to attend regularly. It would help if there were more training centers closer to our homes or transportation support for women.

Vocational training has also been instrumental in fostering entrepreneurship among rural women. Women who learned handicrafts, embroidery, or tailoring reported starting their own small businesses, often working from home to cater to local demand. The entrepreneurship modules in the vocational training programs helped participants learn the basics of running a business, including financial management, pricing strategies, and customer service.

Response 4

I now sew clothes and do embroidery work for people in my village. This has increased my income, and I can now contribute about 3,000 to 5,000 rupees a month. I recently bought a small sewing machine with my savings, which helps me work faster and take on more orders.

A recurring theme in the interviews was the sense of economic independence and improved social status

that vocational training provided. Many women expressed pride in contributing financially to their households. They reported greater respect from family members and the community, as their earnings helped alleviate financial burdens. Several participants mentioned that their ability to earn an income had improved their decision-making power within their families, particularly regarding household expenditures and children's education. This shift in social dynamics indicates that vocational training not only empowers women economically but also strengthens their roles within their families and communities.

Response 5

Vocational training has significantly improved my financial situation and earning capacity. Before receiving this specialized training, my income was limited due to the lack of practical skills needed in high-demand fields. However, the hands-on skills I acquired allowed me to pursue better-paying job opportunities in industries where these skills are highly valued.

Response 6

Before joining, I thought economic empowerment was only about having a job. But now, it means being able to make my own decisions, like spending on my children's education without waiting for my husband's approval. The training has helped me feel more respected at home and in my community.

Women who started their own ventures highlighted that the training had boosted their confidence in managing finances and making independent business decisions. Some participants had even formed small cooperatives with other trained women to share resources and expand their customer base. These cooperative efforts enabled them to scale their businesses beyond the local level, supplying products to nearby towns and cities.

Response 7

The training boosted my confidence. I used to be very shy, but now I feel more assertive when talking to people. My husband has noticed this change, and he supports me. The other women in my family look up to me and are even thinking of joining similar programs.

Response 8

I've gained a lot of confidence. I can talk to people about my work and even make decisions about how to spend the money I earn. I feel like an important member of my family now.

FINDINGS

The findings from this study illustrate that vocational training has a transformative impact on the lives of rural women in Hyderabad, fostering financial independence, improving self-confidence, and shifting family and community dynamics. Economic Independence was a central theme, with participants consistently reporting newfound financial autonomy after acquiring vocational skills in areas such as sewing, embroidery, and bookkeeping. Many women described how these skills allowed them to generate income, support their families, and even save for future needs. This additional income reduced financial pressure on their households and gave women a direct role in contributing to family finances.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study align with existing research that suggests vocational training can be a powerful tool for the economic empowerment of rural women. However, the sustainability of the benefits derived from vocational training depends on several external factors, including market access, financial support, and infrastructure. For vocational training to have a lasting impact, there needs to be a concerted effort to provide women with ongoing support post-training. This could include mentorship

programs, financial assistance, and access to larger markets. Furthermore, vocational training programs should be designed to be flexible and adaptable to the specific needs and constraints of rural women, many of whom must balance economic activities with household responsibilities.

CONCLUSION

Vocational training has a profound impact on the economic empowerment of rural women in Hyderabad. It enhances their employability, provides them with the skills necessary to start small businesses, and contributes to household income and community development. However, for these gains to be sustainable, it is crucial to address challenges related to market access, financial support, and ongoing training. However, the long-term success of these initiatives requires additional support, particularly in terms of market access and financing for women-owned businesses. The research highlights the need for a more holistic approach to vocational training, which includes post-training support systems and links to broader economic networks. By addressing these gaps, vocational training can become an even more effective tool for promoting sustainable economic empowerment among rural women. Future policies and programs should focus on providing rural women with comprehensive training that includes entrepreneurial development and post-training support. By doing so, vocational training can become a more effective tool for the long-term economic empowerment of women in rural Hyderabad

RECOMMENDATIONS

Implementing mentorship programs and providing access to microfinance for women who complete vocational training programs. Establishing connections between rural women entrepreneurs and urban markets through various platforms. Regularly assessing the effectiveness of vocational training programs and the long-term impact on women's economic activities to ensure continuous improvement. Designing training programs that consider the unique constraints and opportunities in rural areas, such as integrating mobile training units or offering flexible schedules to accommodate women's responsibilities. Expanding the reach of vocational training programs in rural areas through mobile training units and partnerships with local NGOs.

REFERENCES

- Agarwal, S., Lenka, U., Singh, K., Agrawal, V., & Agrawal, A. M. (2020). *A qualitative approach towards crucial factors for sustainable development of women social entrepreneurship: Indian cases*. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 274, 123135.
- Andriamahery, A., & Qamruzzaman, M. (2022). *Do access to finance, technical know-how, and financial literacy offer women empowerment through women's entrepreneurial development?*. *Frontiers in psychology*, 12, 776844.
- Bullough, A., Guelich, U., Manolova, T. S., & Schjoedt, L. (2022). *Women's entrepreneurship and culture: gender role expectations and identities, societal culture, and the entrepreneurial environment*. *Small Business Economics*, 58(2), 985-996.
- Ebrahimi, R., Choobchian, S., Farhadian, H., Goli, I., Farmandeh, E., & Azadi, H. (2022). *Investigating the effect of vocational education and training on rural women's empowerment*. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 9(1).
- Factors affecting women entrepreneurs' success: a study of small-and medium-sized enterprises in emerging market of Pakistan*. *Journal of innovation and entrepreneurship*, 10, 1-21.
- Farrukh, M., Ghazzawi, I., Raza, A., & Shahzad, I. A. (2021). *Can religiosity foster intrapreneurial behaviors? The mediating role of perceived organizational support*. *World Journal of Entrepreneurship, Management and Sustainable Development*, 17(3), 354-371.

- Grundall, K., & Mack, A. (2023). *Influencing Students' Technical Vocational Education and Training Career Path:: A Qualitative Research*. *Caribbean Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 2(1), 165-198.
- Khalid, A. ., Aashiq, U. ., Iqbal, M. S. ., & Hassan, S. S. . (2020). *Impact of Vocational Training on Economic Empowerment of Youth in Rural Areas of Punjab*. *Review of Education, Administration & Law*, 3(2), 341-350. <https://doi.org/10.47067/real.v3i2.76>
- Malureanu, A., Panisoara, G., & Lazar, I. (2021). *The relationship between self-confidence, self-efficacy, grit, usefulness, and ease of use of elearning platforms in corporate training during the COVID-19 pandemic*. *Sustainability*, 13(12), 6633.
- Nyimbili, F., & Nyimbili, L. (2024). *Types of Purposive Sampling Techniques with Their Examples and Application in Qualitative Research Studies*. *British Journal of Multidisciplinary and Advanced Studies*, 5(1), 90-99.
- Omer, S., Zakar, R., Zakar, M. Z., & Fischer, F. (2021). *The influence of social and cultural practices on maternal mortality: a qualitative study from South Punjab, Pakistan*. *Reproductive health*, 18(1), 97.
- Parveen, R. (2023). *Vocational Skill Development Imperative for Women Empowerment in India*. *Journal of Women Empowerment and Studies (JWES) ISSN: 2799-1253*, 3(03), 15-24.
- Samoliuk, N., Bilan, Y., & Mishchuk, H. (2021). *Vocational training costs and economic benefits: exploring the interactions*. *Journal of Business Economics and Management*, 22(6), 1476-1491
- Tiwari, P., & Malati, N. (2023). *Role of training in women empowerment: an empirical analysis: women empowerment*. *Journal of Technical Education and Training*, 15(1), 234-245.

APPENDIX

1. *What motivates you to participate in vocational training programs?*
2. *What types of skills or trades are you interested in learning, and why?*
3. *What challenges have you faced during vocational training?*
4. *How has vocational training impacted your financial situation or earning capacity?*
5. *How has the training impacted your confidence, decision-making abilities, or social standing?*
6. *What impact has the training had on your personal confidence and self-esteem?*
7. *How accessible was the vocational training, and what improvements would you suggest?*